
ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ

УДК 159.99

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7273100

ОСОБЕННОСТИ РЕШЕНИЯ КЛАССИФИКАЦИОННЫХ ЗАДАЧ В НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ШКОЛЕ

CHARACTERISTICS OF PROBLEM SOLVING OF CLASSIFICATION PROBLEMS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

ЗАК АНАТОЛИЙ ЗАЛМАНОВИЧ,

ведущий научный сотрудник,

Психологический институт Российской академии образования.

ZAK ANATOLY ZALMANOVICH,

leading researcher,

Psychological institute of the Russian academy of education.

В статье представлено исследование, направленное на определение особенностей решения классификационных задач учащимися третьего и четвертого классов. В индивидуальных экспериментах с 53 младшими школьниками (27 третьеклассниками и 26 четвероклассниками) было предложено решать задачи на группировку сложных графических объектов сначала в наглядно-образной форме, а затем в материальной форме. Было показано, что при группировке в материальной форме успешность решения задачи классификации возрастает. Этот факт важен для оценки способностей младших школьников в решении классификационных задач, связанных с группировкой сложных графических объектов.

The article presents a study aimed at determining the features of solving classification problems by students of the third and fourth grades. In individual experiments with 53 junior schoolchildren (27 third-graders and 26 fourth-graders), it was proposed to solve problems for the grouping of complex graphic objects, first in a visual-figurative form, and then in a material form. It was shown that when grouping in material form, the success of the solution classification problem increases. This fact is important for assessing the capabilities of younger students in solving classification problems related to the grouping of complex graphic objects.

Ключевые слова: *третьеклассники, четвероклассники, классификационные задания, действия сравнения в наглядно-образной форме, действия сравнения в материальной форме.*

Key words: *third-graders, fourth-graders, classification tasks, comparison actions in a visual-figurative form, comparison actions in a material form.*

Introduction

The Federal State Educational Standard of Primary General Education contains provisions according to which the meta-subject results of mastering the basic educational program of primary

general education should reflect, in particular, the mastery of the logical actions of comparison, analysis, synthesis, generalization and classification [7].

These provisions characterize the relevance of our study, which is devoted to the study of the possibilities of younger schoolchildren, in particular, students of the third and fourth grades, in applying the logical actions of classification in solving problems "to form classes."

1.1. Features of classification problems

When solving problems of this type, comparison of objects requires a formal relationship to them, operating with all their available properties and choosing from the proposed objects the necessary properties and features that are necessary in accordance with the requirements of the task.

Accounting for these requirements imposed on the actions of the subject by the characteristics of the mentioned types of tasks is necessary for a successful psychological analysis of solving problems "for classification". In particular, the fact that younger schoolchildren, and especially preschoolers, have difficulty coping with tasks of this type is connected, from our point of view, with the fact that children do not have a formal relationship to the objects of comparison, characterized by the perception of the object as to a set of potentially equally desirable properties.

This is not surprising, since the entire life experience of the child does not imply the formation of such an attitude towards objects. On the contrary, by assimilating various actions with objects in everyday life and in play, the child develops a functional, "selfish" attitude towards objects, associated with the allocation of necessary and unnecessary, main and non-principal (secondary) properties and features in them. Therefore, when faced with the task of "classifying" – where it is impossible to judge the signs a priori (that is, before comparison), dividing them into main and non-main ones – children cannot succeed.

In "classification" tasks, an essential feature is understood as one that satisfies the requirements of the instruction, i.e., repeats the required number of times. In this case, the qualification of a sign as essential is made not in relation to the method of using this object, but in relation to the situation in which this object is compared with others, i.e., in relation to the requirement to take into account the required number of objects.

For classification tasks, it is more expedient to use the terms "important" and "unimportant" feature, as indicating exactly the relative, situational significance of a particular feature. This will greatly simplify the analysis of situations related to the classification of real objects (i.e., things created by man) by their size or color.

The use of the terms – "important" and "unimportant" sign – creates opportunities for consistent comparison of the content of research into solving classification problems, performed both on real and artificial material. We note, in passing, that the question of the material of classification problems as one of the determinants of the implementation of certain strategies for their solution was considered in a number of works (see, for example, [5; 6]), where it was shown that classification is carried out on artificial material better than the real one.

The difficulty of classification problems is not determined unambiguously and directly by the type of material proposed for classification. We believe that the decisive condition for successful classification is not the material itself, but the interaction of the subject's previous experience (including, in particular, his attitude to the proposed objects) and the instructions of the classification task. An important aspect of such interaction is the extent to which the material of the problem prevents the subject from relating formally to the objects of comparison.

Here, various combinations of experience and instruction are possible, both in the case of real objects and in the case of artificial objects. So, the easiest tasks can be considered those in which an important feature for a given group of objects is also important for the subject. This may be the case if in the previous experiment real objects were used only with an orientation to this feature (for example, color for pencils).

For artificial objects, on the other hand, a bright, catchy sign for direct observation, for example, some unusual protrusion or a strange-shaped hole in three-dimensional objects, or a bizarre line in graphic objects, can act as important for the instruction and important for the subject. Thus, the easiest tasks will be those in which the subject does not need to abandon the habitual attitude to real objects or the initial (by impression) attitude to artificial objects.

More difficult will be tasks in which an important feature coincides with one of those features that the subject has already been guided by when acting with these objects in a previous experiment. In the case of artificial objects, the tasks for classifying the same (medium) degree of difficulty will be those in which objects have several equally bright and catchy features. The main difficulty of tasks of this type is that the subject must consider any of the features of the object as potentially important for the requirements of this task.

1.2. Types of thinking in solving classification problems

When considering issues related to the specific features of classification tasks, one should especially dwell on the possibility of qualifying the two types of attitude of the subject to the objects of classification that we have identified in the context of ideas about empirical and theoretical thinking [2; 3; 4].

So, the attitude of a person to the objects of classification, due to the fact that they are evaluated only on the basis of the initial impression, which assigns the status of an important one to some (outwardly catchy or fairly well-known) sign, can be considered characteristic of the empirical approach to solving classification problems. This follows from the fact that empirical thinking is characterized by dependence on the random features of a single object.

A different attitude of a person to objects of classification is associated with considering them as sets or sets of equivalent features, any of which may be important. At the same time, for a person, there is a distinction between the ideal essence (when objects are thought of as sets of equivalent features) and real existence (when objects are directly observed as sets of features different in meaning for a person – some are more familiar, others are less, some are simpler, others are more complicated, etc. Such a distinction distinguishes theoretical thinking, a theoretical approach to solving problems, from an empirical one.

2. Materials and methods

The purpose of this study was to study the nature of the dependence of the way of thinking on the form of action in solving classification problems related to the formation of classes from the proposed objects. It was assumed that the more specific the form of action, the more successful the solution of problems of the type under consideration. Two series of individual experiments were carried out.

2.1. First series

The purpose of this series was to identify strategies for solving classification problems based on the grouping of abstract images.

2.1.1. Characteristics of the experimental technique

The following problem was used as a technique for the first series (Fig. 1):

On fig. 1 shows nine relatively large (according to the area occupied in Fig. 1) geometric bodies – cylinders. In two parts of the lateral surface of the cylinders, small geometric figures are placed – rhombuses, squares, pentagons, circles, a triangle. Four-pointed stars are depicted on the round bases of the cylinders.

In this problem, it was required to find five (no more and no less) cylinders that are most suitable for each other.

In this series, as noted, the methods or strategies used by children in solving a given classification problem were clarified. Pupils of grades 3 and 4 participated in individual experiments – 27 and 26 people, respectively.

Fig. 1. Cylinders.

To demonstrate the features of different strategies used by the subjects in the classification, a sign model was developed that displays the features of each of the nine images of cylinders in the form of a combination of letters and numbers, for example:

A 1 B 7 V	E 2 C 8 W	U 3 B 7 W
(1)	(2)	(3)
A 2 D 7 W	U 1 B 8 W	I 2 D 7 W
(4)	(5)	(6)
I 3 B 8 V	E 3 D 7 V	A 2 D 8 W
(7)	(8)	(9)

In this model of the conditions of the problem for the classification of abstract geometric patterns, the location of the sign reflects the type of feature, and the sign itself is one of the variants of the feature of this type.

So, the extreme letters on the left - the vowels A, E, U, I – display such a sign as the orientation of the cylinder in the plane of the sheet: from left to right (images 1, 4, 9, – letter A), from bottom to top (images 2, 8, – letter E), from right to left (images 3, 5, – letter U), from top to bottom (images 6, 7, – letter I).

The numbers 1, 2, 3 display such a sign as a line dividing the side surface of the cylinder into two parts. This sign has three options: single line (images 1, 5, 9, – number "1"), double line (images 2, 4, 6, – number "2"), triple line (images 3, 7, 8, – the number "3").

The middle letters, consonants B, C, D, display such a sign as the appearance of a figure located between an invisible base and a dividing line. This sign has three variants: square (images 1, 3, 5, 7, letter B), triangle (image 2, letter C), circle (images 4, 6, 8, 9, letter D).

The numbers 7 and 8 display such a sign as the appearance of a figure located between the visible base and the dividing line. This sign has two options: a rhombus (images 1, 3, 4, 6, 8 – number 7) and a pentagon (images 2, 5, 7, 9 – number 8).

The letters V and W display such a sign as the position of a four-pointed star in relation to the line dividing the side surface of the cylinders. This feature has two options: a star whose rays are

located at an angle of 90° to the dividing line (images 1, 7, 8 – the letter V) and a star whose rays are located at an angle of 45° to the dividing line (images 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 9 – the letter W).

2.1.2 Strategies for solving the problem

Observations of the solution of the problem noted above made it possible to single out two groups of strategies for its solution.

2.1.2.1. The first group of strategies

There were three strategies in this group, A, B, and C. With strategy A, the subject acted as follows. Having marked any image of a cylinder with a pencil, for example, image 1 (A 1 B 7 V), the subject singled out some element (feature) in it, for example, the letter A and looked for an image that contains this element, and found, for example, image 4 (A 2 D 7 W). In this case, the newly found image was immediately marked (recall that, according to the instructions of this technique, five images had to be marked).

Then the subject returned to the first image 1 (A 1 B 7 V) and singled out another element in it, for example, the number 1. Further, in the process of examining the images, this element was in image 5 (U 1 B 8 W), which was also immediately noted. Acting in the same way, the subject marked image 7 (I 3 B 8 V), where there is a common element with the image A 1 B 7 V - the letter B, and also marked images 3 (U 3 B 7 W) and 4 (A 2 D 7 W), where there is a common element with the image A 1 B 7 CV, – number 7).

Illustrating this strategy with the real actions of the subjects, it can be noted that, first, in image 1, such a feature as the position of the cylinder in the sheet plane (in particular, the “left to right” position) was distinguished, then another feature, the dividing line (in particular, “single”), then – the third sign, – a figure at the invisible base of the cylinder (in particular, “square”) and, finally, the fourth sign, – a figure at the base (in particular, “rhombus”).

With strategy B, the subjects acted differently: they marked adjacent images, for example, 1 (A 1 B 7 V) and 4 (A 2 D 7 W), finding a common element A in them. Then two other adjacent images were marked, for example, 2 (E 2 C 8 W) and 6 (I 2 D 7 W), which have common elements - the number 2 and the letter W.

But since it was required to mark five images, the subjects in this case marked one more image, either 9 (A 2 D 8 W) or 8 (E 3 D 7 V), i.e. any adjacent image that has some common element with the image 6 (I 2 D 7 W), for example, the letter D.

Illustrating this strategy with the real actions of the subjects, it can be noted that in adjacent images 1 and 4 such a feature was distinguished as the position of the cylinder in the plane of the sheet (in particular, its position “from left to right”), in neighboring images 2 and 6 another feature was distinguished, – a dividing line (in particular, “double”) and in one of the neighboring ones with image 6, in image 9 or 8, such a sign as a circle stood out.

Strategy B was implemented in this way. Having marked image 3 (U 3 B 7W), the subject then marked image 5 (U 1 B 8 W), which has many common elements - U, B, W with image 3. Then they noted: image 7 (I 3 B 8 V), where there are elements B and 8 common with the image 5; image 1 (A 1 B 7 V), where there are elements B and V in common with image 7; image 4 (A 2 D 7 W), where there are elements A and 7 in common with image 1.

There were other sets of images, but the principle of their selection remained identical: images were noted that had pairwise common elements.

Illustrating this strategy with the real actions of the subjects, it can be noted that at first, in images 3 and 5, such general features were distinguished as the position of the cylinder in the plane of the sheet (in particular, the position “from right to left”), the figure at the invisible base (in particular, the square) and the position a four-pointed star in the visible base (in particular, at an angle of 45° to the dividing line).

Then, in images 5 and 7, such common features as a figure at the invisible base of the cylinder (in particular, a square) and a figure at the visible base (in particular, a pentagon) were distinguished.

Further, in images 7 and 1, such common features were distinguished as a figure at the invisible base of the cylinder (in particular, a square) and the position of a four-pointed star in the visible base (in particular, at an angle of 90° to the dividing line).

After that, in images 1 and 2, such common features as the position of the cylinder in the plane of the sheet (in particular, the “left to right” position) and the figure at the visible base (in particular, the pentagon) were distinguished.

These strategies for solving the classification problem by the subjects have a number of common features. Thus, the subjects always immediately noted the image in which an element was found that was common to at least two images. In our opinion, this indicates that the subjects made a substitution of the task. The fact is that in the task it was required to find five images that are most suitable for each other among nine images, and not just find images that are suitable for each other.

In other words, in these images it was necessary to select an element that would be repeated only five times, no more and no less. However, the actions of the subjects indicate that they considered it sufficient to isolate signs that are simply repeated, no matter how many times this happened.

It can be said that for these subjects, the entire set of elements in the drawings was divided into only two groups: repetitive and non-repeating, while in order to successfully solve the tasks, it was also necessary to single out two groups among the repetitive ones: repeating five times and repeating any another number of times.

It should be noted that the groupings resulting from actions according to the indicated strategies are complexes as a special form of combining objects, analyzed in detail by L.S. Vygotsky [1]. According to his ideas, complexes “... are a generalization or a union of specific heterogeneous objects. ... Any connection can lead to the inclusion of a given element in the complex, if only it is actually available, and this is the most characteristic feature of the construction of the complex. ... Each element of the complex can be associated with the whole, expressed in the complex, and with the individual elements that make up its composition, with a variety of connections ... ” [1, p.170].

In our case, combining images according to strategy A is similar to building an associative complex, where image 1 (A 1 B 7 V) acts as its center, and combining images according to strategy C is typical for building a chain complex in which images that do not follow one another when combined, may not have a common element, for example, images 5 (U 1 B 8 W) and 4 (A 2 D 7 W), and yet they will belong to the same group.

The noted features of solving problems by the subjects of both groups make it possible to qualify the strategies A, B, C (used by the subjects of the first group) as a manifestation of the empirical method of solving these classification problems, since it is directly related to the objects of classification.

2.1.2.2. The second group of strategies

This group of strategies includes strategies D and E. In the first of them, the subjects found any two images (most often adjacent ones) and singled out the repeating element in them, for example, images 1 (A 1 B 7 V) and 5 (U 1 B 8 W), which have a common feature – a single dividing line on the side of the cylinders - element 1). But the images were not marked.

Then this sign was checked for repeatability, regulated by the instruction. If the first selected element was not repeated five times, then another element common to these images was selected. If there was no such element (as in this case), then two other images were taken that had some common element, for example, images 1 (A 1 B 7 V) and 4 (A 2 D 7 W), which have common features the position of the cylinder “from left to right” protrudes, and the figure on the visible base of the cylinder is “rhombus”, i.e. elements A and 7.

Checking element A for repeatability revealed only three images where this element is present – images 1, 4 and 9, and checking element 7 showed that there are five images in which this element is present – images 1, 3, 4, 6, 8. Only after that, the found five images were marked with a pencil.

With strategy E, the subjects acted somewhat differently. They chose not two, but one of some images, most often image 1 (A 1 B 7 V). Then they singled out some element in it (for example, the letter A) and checked it for repeatability. If this element did not repeat the number of times corresponding to the requirement of the task, then another element was selected in the same image 1 (for example, the number 1), which was also checked for repeatability.

Then, in case of failure, the next element was selected and so on until the check showed that the selected element (all from the same image 1) was repeated in only five images. Only after that, the images, where the checked element (in this case, the letter number 7) was repeated five times, were marked with a pencil, i.e. images 1, 3, 4, 6, 8.

Thus, the strategies of the second group are characterized by the separation in time of such two links in the solution of the classification problem as the search for the desired feature (i.e., the feature repeated in the required number of images) and fixing the found images that belong to the same group and are included in one class, by marking them with a pencil.

Often it was possible to observe that during the test of the next element, the subjects "held" with their fingers the cylinders, which, according to them, could be included in a group of five images.

In other cases, such images were marked with a barely noticeable dot or thin line, while after checking the five images found, they were marked with a line drawn with strong pressure on the pencil.

Observations of the subjects who used these strategies for classification show that they solved the problem in three stages: highlighting some feature (putting forward a hypothesis about its importance), testing this hypothesis (finding out the number of repetitions of this element) and fixing the group from the desired number of images. Moreover, often after the second stage (in the case when checking the element for repeatability showed its unsuitability), the first stage could again follow, associated with the advancement of a new hypothesis.

We can say that the subjects of the second group (who used the D and E strategies) solved classification problems in a theoretical way, characterized by an indirect attitude to the objects of classification, in which they are considered as sets of equivalent features, despite the fact that in perception they yes as sets of different elements

Thus, as a result of the experiments of the first series, the features of the solution of the problem "to form classes" by empirical and theoretical methods were established.

2.2. Second series

The purpose of this was to determine the nature of the connection between the strategies for solving the problem "to form classes" and the form of action when grouping abstract geometric images. It was assumed that a change in the form of action during the classification of these images leads to a change in the method of solving the classification problem.

We accepted, in particular, that the implementation of the classification in the material form of action should facilitate the transition of the subjects from the empirical method of solving these problems to the theoretical one. For this, a special methodological technique was used – copying graphic objects of classification as a variant of the material form of action.

2.2.1. Features of the second task

In the second series of experiments, only those students of the third and fourth grades participated who, in the first series, unsuccessfully solved the problem "to form classes", implementing the empirical method: – i.e. 17 third graders and 10 fourth graders. They were asked to solve the second problem "on the formation of classes." This task was similar to the first one they dealt with in the previous series (Fig. 2).

First, in the second task, the same five features were used to compare objects of classification: the position of a large figure (a convex pentagon) in the sheet plane, a line dividing the area of a large figure into two unequal parts and three small figures. Secondly, the distribution of feature variants over nine pentagons was the same in the second task as in the first.

Fig. 2. Pentagons.

The noted characteristics of the similarity of both tasks make it possible to use the same model representation of classification objects in the analysis of the second of them as in the first task.

2.2.2. Characteristics of the actions of different groups of subjects

The second series of experiments was organized as follows. One group of subjects, 8 third-graders (out of 17) and 5 fourth-graders (out of 11), who had unsuccessfully solved the first problem empirically, were asked to solve the second problem in the same way as they solved the first one, i.e. in a visual-figurative plan (in the perceptual form of action).

Another group, 9 third-graders (out of 17) and 6 fourth-graders (out of 11), were first asked to copy by copying nine proposed classification objects, i.e. nine large pentagons with five of the above features.

The meaning of such an organization of experiments in this series was to compare the way children act when solving a classification problem again and when solving such a problem with a preliminary copying of its conditions in material form.

3. Results

According to the results of solving the first task in a visual-figurative form, the students of each class were divided into two groups. The first group included 20 third-graders and 16 fourth-graders. These students used strategies A, B and C in solving problems and, in general, could not solve the problem correctly. Sometimes they found the correct group of five images - there were 3 such children in the third grade and 5 in the fourth grade.

However, observations showed that such a result was obtained by chance: as a result of unintentional actions of the subject. Thus, in the first group there were 17 third-graders and 10 fourth-graders who solved the problem incorrectly.

The second group of subjects consisted of the remaining 10 third-graders and 16 fourth-graders, who used D and D strategies when solving problems and solved the problem correctly (see table). Observations showed that these subjects considered the images in the tasks as a set, or a complex of equivalent elements, each of which may be important.

The noted features of solving problems by the subjects of both groups make it possible to qualify the strategies A, B, C (used by the subjects of the first group) as a manifestation of the empirical method of solving these classification problems, since it is directly related to the objects of classification.

The subjects of the second group (using the D and D strategies) solved the same classification problems in a theoretical way, characterized by an indirect attitude to the objects of classification, in which they are considered as sets of equivalent features, despite the fact that in perception they are yes. ns as sets of different elements.

Conducting experiments of the second series showed that only 1 person out of 8 third-graders and 3 people out of 5 fourth-graders (the first group) switched from the empirical solution method (in particular, from strategy B, which he had with solution of the first problem) to the theoretical method, to the strategy D (see table).

The remaining 7 third-graders and 2 fourth-graders of this group also acted unsuccessfully in solving the second problem and used the same strategies of the empirical method as in solving the first one. They were asked to draw images of pentagons in the condition of this problem.

After copying the images, it turned out that 6 children out of 9 third-graders and 5 out of 6 fourth-graders were able to already in the course of copying images (some of them indicate five images that are most suitable for each other (someone did this in the fifth drawing, someone – in seventh), and two third-graders and one fourth-grader had to copy all the images for a successful solution.

Thus, after copying the drawings in the condition of the second problem, one student solved it incorrectly for the third-graders, the fourth-graders did not have such children - all the students solved the problem correctly (see table 1).

Table 1. The number of students in the third and fourth grades who correctly solved the problem in the first and second series in a visual-figurative form and in the second series after copying the drawings.

Classes	The correct solution to the problem visual-figurative form		The correct solution to the problem after copying pictures
	First series	Second series	Second series
Third	10 (37,04%)*	1 (12,50%)	8 (88,89%)
Fourth	16 (61,54%)*	3 (60,00%)	6 (100,00%)

Note: *p < 0.05

Consideration of the results of the study reflected in the table allows us to formulate a number of provisions on the differences in solving problems for the classification of abstract geometric images between students of the fourth and third grades.

Thus, the results of the experiments of the first series indicate that students of the fourth grade are significantly better than students of the third grade in coping with the specified type of classification when acting in a visual-figurative form - the difference between 37.04% and 61.54% is statistically significant (with $p < 0.05$).

In addition, the results of the experiments of the second series, related to the repeated solution of the classification problem in a visual-figurative form, also indicate a greater success of fourth-grade students (result – 60.00%) compared to third-grade students (result – 12.50%) .

Further, the results of the experiments of the second series, related to the solution of the classification problem with preliminary copying (drawing) of abstract geometric images, show that such a methodical technique turned out to be more successful for fourth grade students (result – 100.00%) than for third grade students (result – 88.89%).

Comparison of the results of experiments of the second series, associated with the repeated solution of the classification problem in a visual-figurative form and with preliminary copying in material form, shows an increase in the success of the solution in the latter case.

This fact confirms the initial hypothesis of the study that the more specific the form of action in solving classification problems, the more successful the result.

4. Conclusion

So, the study made it possible to establish the features of the solution by third-graders of classification problems in an empirical and theoretical way.

With further study of the problem of this study, it is planned to identify the features of solving classification problems by other age groups of younger schoolchildren: both students of the second and first grades, and students of the fourth grade.

Based on these studies, it will be possible to more fully present the features of solving classification problems by children of primary school age and determine the main characteristics of the age dynamics of successful and unsuccessful behavioral strategies used by children of this age in problem situations related to the application of the logical action of classification.

СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

1. Выготский Л.С. Избранные психологические исследования. М., 1956. 448 с.
2. Давыдов В.В. Теория развивающего обучения. М.: ИНТОР. 1996. 426 с.
3. Зак А.З. Мышление младшего школьника. Спб.: Содействие. 2004. 828 с.
4. Ильенков Э.В. Диалектическая логика. Очерки истории и теории. М.: Политиздат. 1974. 212 с.
5. Матюшкин А.М., Казанская В.Г. Логические действие и процесс мышления // Новые исследования в психологии и физиологии. Вып. 2. М., 1972. С. 46-58.
6. Пиаже Ж., Инельдер Б. Генезис элементарных логических структур. М., 1963. 276 с.
7. Федеральный государственный образовательный стандарт начального общего образования. М.: Просвещение. 2010. 31 с.

© Зак А.З., 2022.